

flower normally. Data were recorded for primary tillers when anthesis began and when 75% of the florets showed glume senescence.

Entries flowered between the third week of Aug and the first week of Oct. Preanthesis phase ranged from 65 to 125 d (see table). Average period from anthesis to glume senescence (ripening period) varied from 28 to 48 d. Ripening period was not related to length of pre-anthesis period ($r = -0.10$), and the dif-

ferent maturity groups had similar ranges.

Short-duration cultures flowered the last 2 wk of Aug when average temperatures were relatively higher (23.0°C).

Long-duration entries flowered the first week of Oct when average temperatures were lower (17.5°C). The similar range of durations among genotypes of the two groups indicates that the observed variation was not caused by temperature differences and is in fact a varietal character.

Genotypes with short ripening dura-

tion (around 30 d) were Daegaldo and Heug-Jodo (early); Jodo, Mujudo, and Deog-Jeog-Jodo (medium); Kaoshang 27, IR9202-23-2, IAC25, China 988, and Thapuli (medium-long); and C21 and China 4 (long). Long ripening period (around 40 d) was recorded for L 100-A, Nancee, K333, and Kitakogan (early); JC99, IR80-102, Khonorullo, Barmi, and Eiko (medium); Chinan 2, Tapuno, Norin 18, VL 8, and Taichung 176 (medium-long); and Kalimpong (late). □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Reaction of several rice varieties to rice tungro virus (RTV) complex

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The presence of RTV complex in non-IR varieties with different reactions to tungro infection and to its vector, green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*, was determined by latex test using antisera to rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). Eleven-day-old seedlings were mass-inoculated with an average of five tungro-viruliferous insects per seedling. Only plants that exhibited tungro-like symptoms were included in this test.

We also studied the effect of an increased number of viruliferous insects per seedling on RTV complex infection in five resistant varieties: Gam Pai 30-12-15, Pankhari 203, Habiganj DW8, Utri Rajapan, and ARC1 1554. In a screen cage, the seedlings were mass-inoculated with 25 viruliferous GLH/seedling for 3 h with TN1 as the virus source. Healthy TN1 seedlings with one insect per seedling in test tubes were inoculated simultaneously with viruliferous insects taken from this colony. All inoculated plants were evaluated using the latex test.

Results indicated that RTBV and RTSV were generally present in varieties with susceptible and intermediate reactions to

Table 1. Presence of RTBV and RTSV as detected by the latex test in non-IR varieties mass-inoculated by an average of 5 insects/seedling, IRRI.

Variety	Reaction to		Plants tested (no.)	Plants (no.) that reacted to the presence of			Plants (no.) with no reaction
	GLH ^a	RTV ^b		RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	
Gam Pai 30-12-15	R	R	21	0	16	0	5
ARC11554	R	R	11	1	9	0	1
Pankhari 203	MR	R	20	1	16	0	3
Habiganj DW8	MS	R	12	1	11	0	0
Utri Rajapan	MS	R	19	11	8	0	0
Bremli	S	I	22	22	0	0	0
KU115	S	I	19	19	0	0	0
R21	S	I	25	25	0	0	0
Tosidongi	S	I	12	10	2	0	0
Liao-Feng 4	S	I	16	5	11	0	0
Naylamp	MR	S	18	12	6	0	0
ARC5929	S	S	8	8	0	0	0
63-83	S	S	20	19	0	0	1
AUS 100	-	S	18	18	0	0	0
Kuatik Putih	MR	S	24	24	0	0	0
TN1 (check)	S	S	24	21	3	0	0

^a Data from IRRI Entomology Department. ^b Greenhouse mass screening results, IRRI Plant Pathology Department: 0-30% infection = resistant (R), 31-40% = intermediate (I), 60-100% = susceptible (S).

Table 2. Presence of RTBV and RTSV as detected by latex test in resistant non-IR varieties mass-inoculated by an average of 25 insects/seedling, IRRI.

Variety	Plants tested (no.)	Plants (no.) that reacted to the presence of			Plants (no.) with no reaction
		RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	
Gam Pai 30-12-15	21	1	8	0	12
Pankhari 203	21	0	8	0	13
Habiganj DW8	35	0	19	0	16
Utri Rajapan	32	6	12	1	13
ARC11554	41	0	14	0	27
TN1 ^a (check)	19	16	2	0	1

^a Inoculated in test tube at one insect per seedling.

the disease, except for Liao-Feng 4. RTBV alone usually was observed on resistant varieties, except Utri Rajapan (Table 1). Even when the viruliferous insects were increased, infected plants of tungro-resistant varieties usually con-

tained RTBV alone, with the exception of Utri Rajapan (Table 2). Infected resistant varieties developed milder symptoms and were not a virus source for the spread of RTV. □

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GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Screening for resistance to rice hispa

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Rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* (Oliv.) is a sporadic insect pest of transplanted rice. Adult beetles cause parallel white streaks on the leaf. The grubs are leaf miners and cause leaf tissue to wither. In 1983 kharif an unusual outbreak of rice hispa occurred in Ranchi.

To screen for resistance to rice hispa, we planted 64 cultivars of diverse origin in 2 replications in 1.6- × 5-m plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Percent leaves damaged was recorded from 25 randomly selected plants from each plot. Leaf damage ranged from 15.6 to 97%. OR165-94-1 (15.6% damage) and KAU1945 (18.6% damage) were moderately resistant (see table). □

Resistance of rice to rice hispa, Bihar, India.

Score ^a	Damage (%)	Variety
0	No damage	—
1	1-10	—
3	11-20	OR165-94-1, KAU1945
5	21-35	MTU6637, CR341-5-10, NRL326-3, UPR81-44, NDR312, OR79-21, OR158-7-1, RP52-2, RP1848-01-3-2-1, RP1846-219-3-1, BK670, HPU804, RP1575-636-6-1, Rewa 353, RP1442-4-3-1-2, RP1575-243-719-681
7	36-50	NDU127, OR131-5-8, KAU23332-2, FH448, CO 33-83, CN834-1-7-1-2, RP1895-2-1, IR36, UPR254-24-1-1, AS19789, KD5-2-8, NDU83, OR196-2, RP1788-43-2-1-6-2, NDU80, NDR301, RP1888-1441-56-4456, BIET236, UPR79-104, BAU4090-1, Ratna, RP1699-175-112-1, BR1235, RP1831-25-2-2, UPR103-44-2, RP1388-494-145, SKL-6, UPR96-40-2, UPR79-161, Rasi, HKR1, CR268-400-5, HKR78-31, RP1570-44-1, UPR79-123, RGL-2624, RP1699-26-1-1, RAU4056-53-5, NSRP11, RP1699-174-97-1, RP1699-183-133-1, RP1831-20-4-5, RP1898-6, Pusa 245-1-17-1, NDR302, KR10-47.
9	50-100	

^a0-9 scale: 0 = resistant, 9 = susceptible.

Screening rice varieties for resistance to whitebacked planthopper

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Whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* is a serious rice pest in Indonesia. We screened 206 breeding lines for WBPH resistance at the BORIF greenhouse in 1982-83 wet seasons.

A seedbox screening test was used and lines were scored by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (see table). The 33

Performance of 9 lines with resistance to whitebacked planthopper, Bogor, Indonesia.^a

Line	Score ^b	Eggs laid ^c (no.)	Insects (no.) on the plant ^d		
			1 DI	2 DI	3 DI
B3728d-pn-39-3-2	3	11.2 a	8.3 d	10.0 b	8.5 b
B5198b-84-Mr-3	3	13.8 a	7.3 cd	2.0 a	2.5 a
B3825e-Kn-45-2-3	3	11.2 a	7.0 bcd	3.3 a	3.0 a
B3894-17c-Sm-54-2	3	10.8 a	7.3 bcd	4.8 a	4.3 ab
B4032d-Mr-1-3-1	3	13.0 a	3.5 ab	4.8 a	2.5 a
IR5657-33-2-2-3	3	24.8 b	5.0 abcd	3.8 a	5.3 b
IR13240-102-2-Mr-6	3	12.6 a	6.8 abcd	4.0 a	2.3 a
IR5853-198-1-Mr-3-2	3	10.0 a	3.8 abc	4.5 a	1.5 a
IR5853-198-1-Mr-3-3	3	10.6 a	3.8 abc	4.8 a	3.8 a
TN1 (susceptible check)	9	38.6 c	11.8 a	12.0 b	13.5 c
Colombo (resistant check)	3	—	—	—	—
Rathu Heenathi (resistant check)	3	11.2 a	3.25	3.0 a	1.0 a

^aMeans in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 0.05 level.

^bScoring by Standard Evaluation System for Rice: 0 = highly resistant, 9 = susceptible. ^cAv of 5 replications. ^dAv of 4 replications. DI = days after infestation.